

CO₂ flux and carbon stock from smallholder coffee plantation in East Nusa Tenggara

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ABSTRACT

Climate change caused by global warming can have a negative impact on the plantation subsector. Coffee plants in Indonesia are generally cultivated by smallholders in small scale plantations. For plantation products such as coffee and cocoa, the C absorption can be greater than Greenhouse gases (GHG) emissions, making it carbon neutral or even negative carbon throughout their productive time. The objectives of this research were to quantify CO₂ flux and carbon stock in smallholder coffee plantations in Ponto Ara Village, Lembor District, West Manggarai District, East Nusa Tenggara Province. Gas sample was taken using close chamber technique, while gas concentration was measured using a gas chromatography. Estimation of carbon stocks above ground was done by destructive technique, by determining the biomass, and analyzing the carbon content of each part of the plant. Results showed that the smallholder coffee plantation provided flux of 1,684 kg CO₂/ha/month and carbon stock 50 tons CO₂-e/ha while the activities of conservation smallholder coffee gave flux of 2,585 kg CO₂/ha/month and carbon stock 147 tons CO₂-e/ha from above and below biomass.

Keyword: climate change, coffee, GHG, CO₂

INTRODUCTION

Climate change is an environmental issue that gets serious attention from regional, national, and international communities that can threaten life in the future. Climate change that occurs due to global warming can have a negative impact on the agricultural sector such as the crisis of food availability, decreased productivity and declining production of agricultural crops, degradation of land and water resources that can reduce soil fertility and cause pollution, and climate diversity that may lead to a more frequent floods and droughts.

Aside from being victims of climate change impacts, agricultural sector is as neither a source nor a sink of some greenhouse gas (GHGs). The GHGs emissions from the agricultural sector are sourced from rice field, agricultural land, livestock, management of waste/livestock manure, and biomass burning.

Agricultural sector produces three main GHGs, namely carbon dioxide (CO₂), methane (CH₄), and nitrous oxide (N₂O), each of which has a global warming potential index of 1, 25 and 298 (IPCC, 2007).

About 95% of the total plantation area of coffee in Indonesia (1,308,000 ha) is cultivated in small scale (smallholder) plantations. The dominant coffee variety is robusta. Coffee plantations occupy more than 10 million ha globally (FAO, 2011) which with appropriate design and management can potentially decrease CO₂ in the atmosphere and store the C in plant biomass and in the soil. The coffee system is part of a mixed cropping system containing food crops and small numbers of livestock. In some farms fruit trees such as banana, avocado and macadamia are grown along side the coffee trees to supplement incomes from coffee. Farm level activities for smallholder coffee farmers include pruning, handling and desuckering, hand and chemical weeding, fertilizer application, spraying, manure application, mulching and picking (Odhiambo et al., 1996 *cit* Maina, 2017)

Agricultural production systems, especially those that include trees such as coffee plants, have the potential to sequester and store relatively large amounts of C over soil, biomass and soil organic matter (Soto et al., 2010). For plantation products such as coffee and cocoa, the absorption of large C can even be greater than GHG emissions, making it carbon neutral or even negative carbon throughout their productive time. According to Hairiah and Rahayu (2007), the growth rate of carbon stocks in multistrata coffee agroforestry is 0.9-1.86 t/ha/year under the simple agroforestry system (generally belonging to the community) 0.6-0.97 t/ha/year and 2.8 t/ha/year in the experimental garden. While in monoculture coffee only 0.5 t/ha/year.

Mitigation activities aim to reduce greenhouse gas emissions through a strategy to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and increase CO₂ absorption and carbon sequestration. Plantations have a very strategic position in the national action plan in the agricultural sector, because they have a great ability to absorb CO₂. In addition, giving organic matter to the soil is also one way to store carbon. A substantial amount of total global CO₂ emission comes from soil through mineralization and decomposition of organic matter, and respiration of roots and soil organisms (Schlesinger and Andrews, 2000). Plants absorb carbon dioxide gas (CO₂) from air through photosynthesis (Hairiah et al., 2011) and carbon stock from above and below ground biomass. In IPCC (2006) there are 3 'tiers' of data recognized by the 2006 IPCC Guidelines; tier 1 data is country specific but based on global activity, it is the default factor for an emission source and contains a lower level of accuracy as figures are more general.

The purpose of these activities was to measure CO₂ flux and carbon stocks in smallholder coffee plantations in Ponto Ara Village, Lembor District, West Manggarai District, East Nusa Tenggara Province.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This research was carried out in Ponto Ara Village, Lembor District, West Manggarai Regency, East Nusa Tenggara Province, Indonesia on a smallholder farmer's field. Taking sample of gas and biomass is done simultaneously. The condition of the sloping land with altitude ranges from 700-900 m above sea level. The type of land use in the research location is young coffee land that is less than 10 years with a spacing of 2.5 m x 2.5 m with banana tree protective plants.

GHG Flux Measurement

Gas sampling was carried out on 10-26 October 2017 at the location of conventional and conservation people's coffee plantations. Gas sample was taken at 4 sampling points in conventional system and conservation system with using a closed chamber with size of 40 cm length x 20 cm width x 20 cm height according to IAEA (1993). Gas samples were taken every week in October 2017, at three sampling in the morning (06.00-08.00) and daylight hours (12.00-14.00).

Manual sampling time intervals were 10', 20', 30', 40' and 50' since the chambers' top were closed. Gas samples were taken using a 20 ml syringe, then analyzed with a Greenhouse Gases Analyzer 450 Variance equipped by ECD detector. CO₂ flux is calculated using the formula from IAEA (1993):

$$E = \frac{dc}{dt} \times \frac{V_{ch}}{A_{ch}} \times \frac{mW}{mV} \times \frac{273,2}{(273,2 + T)}$$

Where:

E : CO₂ flux (mg/m²/day)

dc/dt : The change in CO₂ concentration over the difference in time (ppm/minute)

V_{ch} : Volume box CO₂ (m³)

A_{ch} : Area box CO₂ (m²)

mW : Molecular weight of CO₂ (g)

mV : Molecular volume (22.41 l) at the standard of temperature (25 °C) and pressure (1 bar)

T : Average temperature insite chamber during sampling (°C); Value 273.2: based on temperature of Kelvin

Data in figure was presented as mean values standard deviations. The SAS 9.1.3 Portable analytical software package was used for all statistical analyses. Statistical analysis was accomplished by standard analysis of variance (ANOVA,) and the differences among treatments used Tukey test to determine significant differences.

Carbon Stock Measurement (C-Stock)

This method is carried out by researchers for the purpose of developing the allometric formula, especially at tree types that have specific branching patterns that have not generally known allometric equations. Development allometric is done by cutting down trees and measuring diameter, the length and weight of his time. Destructive methods are also carried out on understorey, seasonal plants and shrubs (Hairiah et al., 2011).

Carbon stocks above ground was done by destructive technique, weighing the dry weight of biomass, and measuring/analyzing the carbon content of stems, twigs and tree canopies of the plant. We also measured the C-stock biomass of understorey and litter biomass (non-wood necromas). All the litter in the sub-plot was taken and put in a bag, then weighed heavily. Litter sub-samples from each sub-plot were taken about 100-300 grams and dried and analyzed to determine the percent C content of plants in the laboratory.

$$\text{Carbon stock} = \text{Biomass} \times \% \text{ C organic in the plant}$$

Measuring carbon stocks is also done without damaging plant biomass (non-destructive), namely by measuring plant samples, identifying plant species, then calculating them by using certain equations (allometrics) (Table 1). Which is measured by non-destructive method when the measured plant is known for its allometric formula. Where as for tree species that have specific branching patterns that have not it is known that allometric equations are generally measured by destructive means.

Table 1. Estimation of tree biomass using allometric equations

Tree type	Tree Biomass Estimation (kg/tree)
Branched tree	$BK = 0,11 \rho D^{2,62}$
Unbranched tree	$BK = \pi \rho H^* D^2/40$
Coffee	$BK = 0,281 D^{2,06}$
Banana	$BK = 0,030 D^{2,13}$

Source : Hairiah et al., 2011

Description: BK: dry weight or biomass (g); D: Tree diameter (cm); H*: tree height (cm); H**: tree height (m); ρ : wood specific gravity (g/cm^3); Diameter = $\text{Roving}/3.14$

These allometric equations as proposed by IPCC to determine the biomass stored in other tree types apart from coffee, such as tropical moist and wet hardwoods, tropical and temperate pines as well as palm trees.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The pattern of CO₂ flux from smallholder coffee plantations

Soil CO₂ flux

The GHG sampling time also determines the flux. In the morning, it generally produces lower CO₂ fluxes than day and evening in conventional treatments (Figure 1). Flux increases until late afternoon. This is because in the afternoon it is the optimum time for microorganisms to produce CO₂. CO₂ gas produced from decomposition of organic matter is affected by changes in temperature, hydrological conditions. At high temperatures, CO₂ gas is formed in large quantities. Temperature and humidity both air and soil in the tropics are strongly influenced by the type and density of vegetation that covers it. The content of organic matter in the soil positively correlated with CO₂ emissions generated from the soil (Irawan and June, 2011). Organic material is a source of energy for microorganisms activities in the respiration process that produces CO₂. CO₂ gas occurs in aerobic conditions, where decomposer microorganisms such as bacteria and fungi can run optimally.

Figure 1. CO₂ flux based on sampling time

Daily CO₂ flux ranged from 381.14-10,211.27 mgCO₂/m²/day on smallholder coffee plantations that were managed conventionally and 2159.88-

14,244.08 mgCO₂/m²/day on the community coffee conservation plantations. The results of CO₂ flux measurements were 1,684 kgCO₂/ha/month on smallholder coffee plantations that were managed conventionally and 2,585 kgCO₂/ha/month on the community coffee conservation plantations. CO₂ emissions from the soil are the result of the integration of several factors, including respiration of soil microorganisms and rhizosphere respiration of plants (Ding et al., 2007). Other factors that influence the amount of CO₂ emissions from the soil are soil temperature, soil moisture, depth of groundwater level, fertilization, vegetation type and soil quality, microbial biomass activity and soil management.

Carbon stock from smallholder coffee plantations in East Nusa Tenggara

In this activity can be calculated the amount of carbon stock at the location of conventional coffee plantations, namely as follows:

- Biomass tree = 131 kgC per 5 x 20 m² = 13,100 kgC/ha (Table 2)
- Lower plant weight and litter = 165 gr/m² = 1,650 kg/ha (Table 3)

Carbon stock:

- Tree biomass = 13,100 x 44/12 kgCO₂-e/ha = 48,033 kgCO₂-e/ha
- Lower plants and litter = 1,650 x 0.44 x 44/12 = 2,662 kgCO₂-e/ha
- Organic fertilizer = 10 kg tree⁻¹ x 2000 trees ha⁻¹ x 20/100 x 20/100 x 50/100 x 44/12 = 1,467 kg CO₂-e/ha
- Total carbon stock = 50,695 kgCO₂-e/ha = 50 tCO₂-e/ha

Table 2. Carbon stock on tree biomass (in a conventional plot size 5 m x 20 m)

No	Tree name	Circumference (cm)	Length (cm)	ρ (g/cm ³)	Diameter (cm)	Dry weight (kg/tree)	C-biomass (kgC/tree)
1	Bugar wood	18	3000	0.64	6	6.830	3.142
2	Coffee	23	230		7	16.990	7.815
3	Coffee	42	225		13	58.739	27.020
4	Coffee	20	190		6	12.740	5.860
5	Coffee	30	192		10	29.370	13.510
6	Coffee	33	210		11	35.741	16.441
7	Coffee	20	186		6	12.740	5.860
8	Coffee	20	186		6	12.740	5.860
9	Coffee	22	193		7	15.503	7.131
10	Coffee	22	223		7	15.503	7.131
11	Coffee	13	177		4	5.245	2.413
12	Coffee	19	174		6	11.462	5.273
13	Coffee	19	180		6	11.462	5.273
14	Coffee	24	170		8	18.547	8.531
15	Coffee	26	158		8	21.871	10.061
Total (kg)							131.322

Table 3. Mass of understorey and necromass in conventional small plots (0.5 m x 0.5 m)

No	Vegetation	Fresh Weight (g)		Fresh weight of sub plot (g)		Dry weight of sub plot (g)		Dry weight total (g/m ²)
		Leaf	Stem	Leaf	Stem	Leaf	Stem	
1	Understorey 1	80	25	80	25	26	18	44
2	Understorey 2	20	30	20	30	7	31.5	38.5
3	Necromass1	50		50		32.5		32.5
4	Necromass2	59		59		50		50
Sub Total (g m ⁻²)								165

Conventionally managed community coffee plantations have a carbon stock equal to 50 tons CO₂-e/ha from above and below ground.

Table 4. Carbon stocks on tree biomass (in a 5 m x 20 m conservation plot)

No	Tree name	Circumference (cm)	Length (cm)	ρ (g/cm ³)	Diameter (cm)	Dry weight (kg/tree)	C-biomass (kgC/tree)
1	Coffee	12	160	0.64	4	4.448	2.046
2	Coffee	5	100		2	0.733	0.337
3	Coffee	13	167		4	5.245	2.413
4	Coffee	24	172		8	18.547	8.531
5	Coffee	20	200		6	12.740	5.860
6	Coffee	12	180		4	4.448	2.046
7	Coffee	24	152		8	18.547	8.531
8	Coffee	22	160		7	15.503	7.131
9	Coffee	26	148		8	21.871	10.061
10	Coffee	19	162		6	11.462	5.273
11	Coffee	25	250		8	20.174	9.280
12	Coffee	15	300		5	7.043	3.240
13	Coffee	18	270		6	10.254	4.717
14	Coffee	13	145		4	5.245	2.413
15	Coffee	20	130		6	12.740	5.860
16	Coffee	20	190		6	12.740	5.860
17	Coffee	14	185		4	6.110	2.811
18	Coffee	13	205		4	5.245	2.413
19	Coffee	20	135		6	12.740	5.860
20	Coffee	26	140		8	21.871	10.061
21	Coffee	18	150		6	10.254	4.717
22	Coffee	18	180		6	10.254	4.717
23	Coffee	16	166		5	8.045	3.701
24	Coffee	18	133		6	10.254	4.717
25	Coffee	20	167		6	12.740	5.860
26	Coffee	19	178		6	11.462	5.273
27	Coffee	16	183		5	8.045	3.701

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No	Tree name	Circumference (cm)	Length (cm)	ρ (g/cm ³)	Diameter (cm)	Dry weight (kg/tree)	C-biomass (kgC/tree)
28	Banana	79	400		25	28.881	13.285
29	Banana	65	400		21	19.062	8.768
30	Banana	77	400		25	27.346	12.579
31	Banana	42	250		13	7.519	3.459
32	Banana	74	400		24	25.126	11.558
33	Banana	68	400		22	20.985	9.653
34	Banana	77	400		25	27.346	12.579
35	Banana	55	400		18	13.355	6.143
36	Banana	58	400		18	14.954	6.879
37	Banana	61	400		19	16.650	7.659
38	Gamal	25	170	0.64	8	16.152	7.430
39	Gamal	55	152	0.64	18	127.458	58.631
40	Dadap	27	260	0.64	9	19.760	9.090
41	Avocado	67	7000	0.55	21	183.703	84.503
Total (kg)							389.644

Table 5. Dry weight of understorey and necromass in small conservation plots (0.5 m x 0.5 m)

No	Vegetation	Fresh weight (g)		Fresh weight of sub plot (g)		Dry weight of sub plot (g)		Dry weight total (g/m ²)
		Leaf	Stem	Leaf	Stem	Leaf	Stem	
1	Understorey	270	250	270	250	79.6	106	185.6
2	Necromass	30		30		15.5		15.5
Sub Total (g/m ²)								201.1

Carbon stock in conservation coffee plantations can be calculated as follows:

- Biomass tree = 389 kg/C per 5 x 20 m² = 38,900 kgC/ha (Tabel 4)
- Lower plant weight and litter = 201 gr/m² = 2,010 kg/ha (Tabel 5)

Carbon stock:

- Biomass tree = 38,900 x 44/12 kgCO₂-e/ha = 142,633 kgCO₂-e/ha
- Lower plants and litter = 2,010 x 0.41 x 44/12 = 3,022 kgCO₂-e/ha
- Organic fertilizer = 10 kg/tree x 2000 tree/ha x 20/100 x 20/100 x 50/100 x 44/12 = 1,467 kgCO₂-e/ha
- Total carbon stock = 147,122 kgCO₂-e/ha = 147 tCO₂-e/ha

Conservations managed community coffee plantations have a carbon stock equal to 147 tCO₂-e/ha from above and below ground.

Adaptation and mitigation of GHG on coffee plantation land

Activities of land use change influence soil organic matter (SOC) sink (accumulate additional C). The source C (emit C) or maintain inventory is very important in identifying effective strategies for land-based climate change mitigation. Coffee has an important role in maintaining millions of livelihoods throughout the world. Knowing GHG emissions from coffee plants is important in evaluating options for climate change mitigation in this sector. Soil organic carbon (SOC) is a fundamental property that deals with physical, chemical and biological qualities which is an important component of the global carbon cycle (C) (Magdoff and Van Es. 2009). Shade trees are known as the best solution for the size and quality of coffee beans in addition to supporting the climate (Muschler, 2001) and also result in reduced soil erosion and compaction while increasing the SOC.

The need for continuous intensification of food production has recently been emphasized in the development of global food policy (Foresight, 2011). Given the possible impacts of climate change and the increase in human population (UN. 2009) is a major challenge to achieve it. Such sustainable intensification is to develop an agricultural system that results in increased crop yields without increasing GHG emissions. To achieve the goal there is a need to fully understand the type and amount of GHGs emitted by different food production systems. Therefore increasing the demand to improve and expand the composting strategy with raw material formulations to reduce not only CH₄ and N₂O emissions, but also reduce the significant amount of CO₂ production and total nitrogen and carbon loss of various types of organic waste composting.

The recommended adaptation strategy for this coffee plantation is the use of more shade trees which can reduce the impact of climate change as well as to provide substitutes for products that are of economic value such as fruit trees. The use of legumes as shade crops is also recommended because it can reduce the use of chemical fertilizers and increase the availability of nitrogen in the soil that is moored by these plants. In addition the efficiency of fertilizer use is also important in reducing GHG emissions. Generally farmers provide fertilizer below the recommended dose which does not significantly increase production but increases GHG emissions into the air. Pruning and thinning is done selectively by removing unproductive parts of the plant which will then reduce the level of transpiration and indirectly preserve the soil water content

Some applied mitigation activities are the utilization of plantation crop waste as a source of organic material, animal feed and bio energy sources among others through the development of crop and livestock integration systems; rejuvenation of plantation crops is carried out to increase productivity and carbon sequestration.

CONCLUSION

Conventional smallholder coffee plantation activities provide flux of 1,684 kgCO₂/ha/month and carbon stock 50 tCO₂-e/ha while the activities of conservation smallholder coffee give flux of 2,585 kgCO₂/ha/month and carbon stock 147 tCO₂-e/ha from above and below ground.

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